

Origin Lens: Reclaiming Trust on the AI-Mediated Web Through On-Device Image Provenance Verification

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Abstract

Generative AI enables synthetic visual media at a scale that exceeds human verification capacity. This widens an asymmetry on the Web: users encounter images of uncertain provenance with few practical means of assessment. We present **Origin Lens**, a privacy-first mobile framework that performs cryptographic image provenance verification and AI detection entirely on-device. Built on a Rust/Flutter hybrid architecture, the system combines multiple verification signals—C2PA content credentials, generative model fingerprints, and optional retrieval-augmented context—to provide users with graded confidence indicators at the point of consumption. Unlike centralized platform moderation, this approach allows individuals to verify visual content independently. We discuss how client-side verification infrastructure relates to EU regulatory frameworks (AI Act, DSA) and can complement platform governance for information integrity on the Web.

CCS Concepts

• **Security and privacy** → **Digital rights management**; • **Computing methodologies** → *Computer vision*; • **Information systems** → *Multimedia information systems*.

Keywords

Web Trust, Information Integrity, Image Provenance, C2PA, Visual Misinformation, Privacy-First, On-Device Verification, Generative AI, Web Governance, Socio-Technical Systems

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1 Introduction

The Web has become a major infrastructure through which people encounter news and participate in public discourse. Generative AI introduces a *verification asymmetry* into this ecosystem: synthetic visual media can be produced at scale, yet individual users lack practical tools to assess content authenticity at the point of consumption. This asymmetry undermines trust on the Web—a recurring concern in Web Science research [35]. Prior work in Web Science has examined how the Web’s architecture shapes information flows and vice versa, motivating user-facing verification tools. Large language models have dual-use potential—enabling new disinformation capabilities while offering detection solutions [21]—yet existing mitigation approaches predominantly rely on centralized, platform-level interventions [13]. This creates dependencies on opaque moderation systems and raises surveillance concerns [1], while human factors research indicates that users benefit from immediate, contextual verification signals rather than delayed fact-checks [41].

This paper presents **Origin Lens**, an open-source, privacy-first mobile framework that moves image verification from centralized platforms to individual users.¹ Implementing the C2PA (Coalition for Content Provenance and Authenticity) standard [3] alongside heuristic AI detection, the framework makes provenance verification accessible to non-expert Web users. The contribution is threefold: (1) a privacy-preserving architecture performing verification entirely on-device, (2) a defense-in-depth pipeline combining cryptographic, heuristic, and contextual signals with graded confidence indicators, and (3) a discussion of how client-side verification tools can complement platform governance and regulatory frameworks.

2 Related Work

Recent work in information integrity has focused on robustness evaluation and scalable detection. The *OpenFake* dataset [18] provides deepfake benchmarks, while *Veracity* [6] demonstrates retrieval-augmented fact-checking. Thibault et al. address detection under

¹Source code: <https://github.com/aloth/origin-lens>. Available on the iOS App Store: <https://apps.apple.com/app/id6756628121>. Android support is planned.

distribution shift [39]. Technical detection must be paired with effective human-AI interaction. Lin et al. show psychological inoculation has limited real-time effectiveness [41]. Prior JudgeGPT/RogueGPT studies [22, 25] reveal a perception-accuracy gap [24], and empirical analysis shows cognitive fatigue degrades fake content detection by 10.2 percentage points [25]. Puelma Touzel et al. [32] and Ghafouri et al. [11] observe that information flow complexity and uncertainty communication affect trust calibration. The EU AI Act [9] Articles 50 and 52 mandate machine-readable provenance metadata for AI-generated content, while the Digital Services Act (DSA) [7] requires platforms to implement content moderation transparency. The taxonomy in [24] shows LLMs achieve near-human mimicry (detection scores 0.46–0.50), crossing the “Indistinguishability Threshold” formalized in [20]. The C2PA standard [3] enables decentralized provenance verification, but most tools remain server-dependent. Building on the technical framework introduced in [27], Origin Lens provides a privacy-first, client-side alternative.

Positioning. Existing C2PA verification tools—including Adobe’s Content Authenticity web inspector and the open-source `c2patool` CLI—require either cloud infrastructure or desktop environments. Mobile solutions such as Truepic operate as cloud-mediated capture pipelines rather than user-facing verification tools. Origin Lens differs in three ways: (1) all cryptographic verification executes on-device with no server dependency, (2) it combines C2PA with heuristic and watermark signals in a defense-in-depth pipeline, and (3) it provides graded confidence indicators designed for non-expert end users at the point of consumption.

3 System Architecture

Origin Lens employs a hybrid mobile architecture designed for performance and memory safety (see Figure 1). The core logic is implemented in **Rust** [30] for its memory safety guarantees [16] when parsing complex binary formats, while the user interface is built with **Flutter** [12] for cross-platform mobile deployment.

Defense-in-Depth Strategy. Given epistemic uncertainty in modern media [11], we implement a four-layer pipeline: (1) *Cryptographic Provenance*—parse JUMBF boxes to validate C2PA manifests, verify X.509 trust chains, and compute SHA-256 hashes ensuring hard binding [3, 17, 43]; (2) *Heuristic Metadata*—analyze EXIF/IPTC for generative model artifacts (e.g., Stable Diffusion parameters); (3) *Watermark Detection*—detect imperceptible watermarks (e.g., SynthID) via API [4, 14, 15]; (4) *Contextual Verification*—opt-in reverse image search for prior attributions. Figure 2 shows the resulting decision workflow.

Privacy and Uncertainty Communication. In contrast to cloud-based detection services, Origin Lens processes C2PA and metadata entirely on-device via FFI bindings, following Privacy by Design principles [2] with privacy as the default. Cryptographic provenance and heuristic metadata analysis require no network access. Contextual verification (reverse image search) transmits image data to external services, leaving digital traces; this feature is therefore strictly opt-in and disabled by default, aligning with GDPR Article 25 data minimization [8, 44]. Communicating uncertainty is a known challenge [11]. Origin Lens implements a hierarchical confidence model: *high* (valid C2PA with trusted root), *medium*

Figure 1: Origin Lens architecture: Flutter UI, verification pipeline, FFI bridge, and Rust core. Cryptographic operations execute on-device below the processing boundary.

(EXIF patterns, watermarks), and *low* (opt-in reverse image search requiring user interpretation).

4 Security & Threat Modeling

We applied STRIDE threat modeling [36] to the Origin Lens verification pipeline, analyzing each architectural layer (Figure 1) for potential attack vectors.

Trust Model. Origin Lens relies on two trust anchors: (1) the C2PA trust list—root certificate authorities whose signatures are accepted as valid provenance—and (2) the integrity of the on-device binary. The system does not trust the network, the image source, or remote servers for core verification, reducing the attack surface to the local trust store and application package.

Identified Threats. At the *Verification Pipeline* layer, we identify three STRIDE-categorized risks: (1) *Manifest Stripping* (Tampering)—adversaries remove C2PA metadata during redistribution, a known limitation of content credentials [3]; (2) *Certificate Spoofing* (Spoofing)—attackers forge X.509 certificates to inject false provenance claims; and (3) *Denial of Service*—crafted manifests with deeply nested JUMBF boxes could cause excessive parsing time or memory exhaustion. At the *Cross-Language Bridge*, malformed input could trigger undefined behavior across the FFI boundary [31]; Rust’s ownership model mitigates this by enforcing memory safety at compile time. The *User Interface* faces Information Disclosure risks if verification results are cached insecurely, and Repudiation risks if users cannot confirm verification correctness.

Mitigations. Origin Lens enforces hard binding validation [3]: SHA-256 hashes bind the manifest to image content—any modification invalidates the credential. Against spoofing, a local trust store validates certificate chains against known root authorities; we implement certificate pinning, enforce validity windows, and reject revoked certificates via embedded revocation lists. Against

Figure 2: Analysis workflow: images with C2PA manifests undergo cryptographic verification; others fall back to EXIF-based heuristic detection.

denial of service, the parser enforces depth and size limits on JUMBF structures with bounded memory allocation.

Open Challenges. The analog hole—screen capture or re-photographing behavior. Such a study is planned as the next evaluation phase, building on the dual-axis perception methodology developed in our JudgeGPT research [22]. Ultimately, technical tools alone are insufficient; verification and data literacy remain necessary for societal impact [19, 33]. Complementary approaches such as source-level credibility datasets [23] can augment image-level provenance with domain-level trust signals.

5 Evaluation & Discussion

Performance. On iOS (iPhone 15 Pro), C2PA manifest validation completes in under 500 ms for 12 MP images, EXIF parsing in under 50 ms, and peak memory stays below 45 MB. Server-based verification requires a round trip of 200–800 ms plus image upload, whereas Origin Lens operates locally, avoiding both the latency and privacy cost of data transmission. The Rust core contributes to consistent performance: binary parsing runs without garbage-collection pauses, and the FFI bridge adds negligible overhead (< 1 ms per call). These results indicate that on-device provenance verification is practical for interactive use on current mobile hardware.

Result Communication. Origin Lens presents verification outcomes through a traffic-light-inspired UI [38, 42] with four states: *green* (valid C2PA from trusted root), *purple* (C2PA/EXIF indicating generative origin), *orange* (missing manifest or parse error), and *red* (hash mismatch or broken chain). This encoding was chosen because color-coded status displays reduce interpretation time compared to textual labels [42], and the traffic-light metaphor shows high comprehension in security-indicator studies [38].

Limitations. C2PA effectiveness depends on ecosystem adoption [3]. Adversarial actors may employ manifest stripping or analog-hole attacks. Heuristic detection faces distributional shift as models evolve [5, 28, 29, 37, 39, 40], and demographic predictors show weaker effects for AI-generated content [26]. The current evaluation covers a single device; broader benchmarking across device classes (mid-range Android, older iOS) and formats (HEIF, WebP, RAW) would strengthen generalizability. Critically, the present work evaluates technical performance but does not include a user

study measuring whether participants correctly interpret verification signals or how these affect trust calibration and sharing behavior. Such a study is planned as the next evaluation phase, building on the dual-axis perception methodology developed in our JudgeGPT research [22]. Ultimately, technical tools alone are insufficient; verification and data literacy remain necessary for societal impact [19, 33]. Complementary approaches such as source-level credibility datasets [23] can augment image-level provenance with domain-level trust signals.

Data Availability. The Origin Lens source code is available at <https://github.com/aloth/origin-lens> under GPLv3. Related research datasets are archived on Zenodo: RogueGPT stimulus corpus (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18703138), JudgeGPT perception data (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18703385), and the CRED-1 domain credibility dataset (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19355308).

Regulatory Alignment. Origin Lens aligns with EU regulations that increasingly affect Web governance. Table 1 maps relevant requirements to framework features.

User Interface. Figure 3 shows Origin Lens in three verification scenarios. Table 2 details the four verification states communicated through a traffic-light-inspired visual language.

Figure 3: Origin Lens verification results: (a) valid C2PA manifest with trusted chain, (b) AI-generated content detected via metadata, (c) parsing issue with incomplete chain.

Table 1: Regulatory alignment of Origin Lens features.

Regulation	Requirement	Alignment	User Benefit
EU AI Act	Art. 50, 52: Machine-readable provenance for AI content	C2PA parsing; AI metadata detection	Verify AI origin at point of consumption
GDPR	Art. 25: Privacy by Design; Art. 5: Data minimization	On-device processing; no server transmission	No personal data leaves the device
DSA [7]	Art. 14, 17: Moderation transparency	Independent client-side verification	User agency beyond platform controls
Cyber Resilience Act [10]	Security-by-design for digital products	Rust memory safety; X.509 validation	Reduced memory corruption risk

Table 2: Verification status indicators.

Status	Color	Condition
Verified	Green	Valid C2PA manifest with trusted certificate chain
AI Generated	Purple	AI origin detected via C2PA or EXIF markers
Warning	Orange	Missing manifest, expired certificate, or parse error
Invalid	Red	Hash mismatch or broken certificate chain

6 Conclusion and Future Directions

As generative AI increases the volume of synthetic content on the Web, verification tools that operate independently of centralized platforms become relevant. Origin Lens shows that on-device, privacy-first image provenance verification is feasible, combining cryptographic standards (C2PA) with heuristic detection and graded uncertainty communication. The framework provides a client-side complement to platform-level governance, placing verification capability with the user rather than requiring trust in opaque moderation systems. Treating provenance verification as user-side infrastructure rather than a platform feature is consistent with Web Science research on decentralized trust and user agency.

Several directions remain open. First, lightweight on-device neural networks could enable pixel-level manipulation detection, extending coverage beyond metadata-based signals. Second, privacy-preserving federated aggregation of verification outcomes across users could detect emerging manipulation campaigns without centralizing raw image data. Third, as C2PA adoption grows, cross-jurisdictional alignment of provenance standards will be necessary to ensure interoperability across regulatory regimes. Finally, controlled user studies are needed to measure how on-device verification affects trust calibration, sharing behavior, and information literacy in ecologically valid Web browsing contexts. As our research continues, we invite experts to participate in our survey on verification practices: <https://github.com/aloth/verification-crisis>.

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